

Proceedings of
National Conference

on

**Strategic Management
for
Today's Business**

7th October, 2011

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Strategic Management For Today's Business

Strategic Management For Today's Business

**Edited By
Prof. Atul Kumar**

Chaudhari Atarsingh Yadav Memorial Education Trust's
Siddhant College of Engineering,
Department of Business Management
Pune

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Shri. R. S. Yadav
President

Chaudhari Atarsingh Yadav Memorial Education Trust,
Pune

September 22, 2011

MESSAGE

It is my pleasure to know that the Department of Business Management, Siddhant College of Engineering, is bringing out proceedings to commemorate of its National Conference on very important & timely theme "Strategic Management for Today's Business."

The theme of the conference has been quite attractive and every contemporary thinker should analyze and visualize the role of India in the future. Since the expectations from the management professionals are undergoing a sea change, the management professionals must realize and understand that the good ethics is good profession.

I hope that the proceedings would enlighten the student community and other readers alike and would provide new ideas proposed by qualified speakers during the conference.

With best wishes for the success of the conference.

(R. S. Yadav)

Shri. G. M. Deshmukh
Executive Director

Chaudhari Atarsingh Yadav Memorial Education Trust,
Pune

September 22, 2011

MESSAGE

It is a matter of great pleasure that Department of Business Management, Siddhant College of Engineering, is going to organize a National Conference on "Strategic Management for Today's Business" on 7th October 2011. I hope that a large number of delegates from all over India will deliberate on the topics listed for discussion at the conference.

This conference will provide opportunities to organizations to re-truth, re-position and revitalize their strategies to stand up in this period of dynamic change in business scenario.

Further, I am indeed happy to learn that organizers are going to bring out proceedings of this conference. I congratulate the team working untiringly for this remarkable endeavor and wish all the best for the grand success of the conference and publication of the proceedings.

(G. M. Deshmukh)

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M.B.A,Ph.D.

MESSAGE

I am pleased to note that the Department of Business Management, Siddhant College of Engineering, Pune is bringing out a special commemorative publication coinciding with National Conference on "Strategic Management for Today's Business".

It is only through exchange of information that one can hope to keep up with the rapidly changing world around us. The national conference should cover every important aspect of the strategic management issues for today's business and identify opportunities and challenges before business management professionals and academic scholars.

I hope that conference would provide a platform to exchange the ideas and will develop the knowledge in business management. These efforts will help in promoting the subject as well. This would cater the needs of the industry, academics as well as the new technology

I wish your event a great success.

(Dr. B. V. Sangvikar)

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MESSAGE:

I am happy to know that the Siddhant College of Engineering, Department of Business Management, is bringing out proceeding of the conference on "Strategic Management for today's Business". I wish to congratulate them for the grand success of the event that witnessed large national and international participants.

In today's fast changing business environment, it is necessary to build a culture of consistent high standard with a customer centric approach. Strategy building and execution is an integral part of any business and deeply related to its success.

The high speed of the growth seen in every sector of the industry in India today is much faster than anywhere in this world.
Be it Automobile, Mobile Telephony, Hospitality, Aviation, etc. Every industry is setting a positive trend.

For Example the car penetration rate in India is only 12 cars per 1,000 people as compared to 35 per 1,000 in China and 600 in Europe.
This huge potential is fuelling the exponential growth, in the Indian Automobile Industry.

In fact the growth seen by the western world over 3 long decades is evolving in India within a short span of a single decade.

All of us Indians will be a part of this revolution and contribute to enjoy its benefits in a professional and positive manner.

I am glad that such an initiative is undertaken by your Institute to expose their students on the expectations from the industry in general.

Prashant Gajendragadkar

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Message

I think it's a great idea and initiative to organize a conference on "Strategic Management for Today's Business". As we are reaching out to bigger and better markets every day, we need to calculate each and every move of ours strategically.

Management comprises everything starting from your people, environment, customers and so on, and arranging them in a proper grid of dependencies becomes lot more difficult. So that is where your strategic management comes into picture.

I wish DEPARTMENT OF BUSINESS MANAGEMENT, SIDDHANT COLLEGE OF ENGINEERING all the very best in there endeavors of reaching out the height of Indian and International Business managements.

GOOD LUCK

Regards.

Ashish Garg

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MESSAGE

I would like to take this opportunity to congratulate you as the Department of Business Management of your college is organizing a National Conference on "Strategic Management for Today's Business" at right time when the global business world is facing new challenges. I hope this endeavour on your part would not only help academicians and students to understand the presents scenario and challenges before the business houses but it would also encourage corporate entities to get certain strategic ideas and implement them while designing their plans, projects and programmes.

I wish all the best for the entire success of the conference and expect many more such initiatives from your college in future.

Thanking you.

Your sincerely

Prakash N Chaudhary

Vice-Principal &
Head, Dept.. of Business Law,
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Recipient of the "Best College Award" by the University of Pune

Dr. T. R. Sontakke

Principal

Siddhant College of Engineering,

Pune.

September 20, 2011

MESSAGE

It is our proud privilege that Department of Business Management of our college is organizing National Conference on "Strategic Management for Today's Business" on 7th October 2011.

These days strategic management is necessity of today's business as it is continuously changing its dimensions. Strategic Management is essential to achieve organizational excellence. Continuously excelling in the business performance is the need of the organizations to maintain good financial health. It is possible only when an organization is able to establish an effective link between its process & performance as well as effectively utilize the ultimate potential of every stack holder.

I hope that this conference will generate good literature about the strategic management & business. I believe that this conference will deliberate on varied themes and contribute to the existing knowledge.

I should mention tireless efforts undertaken by organizing committee for this national conference. The organizing committee has made all efforts to ensure the convenience of delegates. Yet there could be few short comings, I owe them all. I appeal you to carry only happy memories with you. Let us join together to make the conference a memorable event.

(Dr. T. R. Sontakke)

Dr. B. N. Gupta

Conference Advisor

September 21, 2011

MESSAGE

It gives me an immense pleasure to be a part of this national conference organized by the Department of Business Management – Siddhant college of Engineering on 7th October 2011. Every conference gives us a platform to discuss the issues openly and opens the door to exchange the opinions by the dignitaries (Industry people, Academicians, Researchers, Students etc.) and reach to the common consensus.

I am sure this conference will definitely be fruitful to the participants from the industry and academic. This conference will prove it's utility as an effective tool of learning to the learned.

I wish all the success of the conference.

(Dr. B. N. Gupta)

PREFACE

I would like to extend my hearty welcome to all. I am grateful to all the distinguished people who readily accept invitation. This national conference on "Strategic Management for Today's Business" is long awaited pleasant undertaking of the Dept. of Business Management, Siddhant College of Engineering, Pune. It is immense pleasure to present the proceedings of the conference on "Strategic Management for Today's Business". This informative multicultural and multidiscipline event explores the platform for participants from academics, industry, and students specially research scholars from the world.

The theme of the conference seemed to be the obvious choice viewing the ripples and repercussions created in today's business scenarios. The theme of the conference comprise all the research activities in the area of OB/HR, Marketing, Entrepreneurship, Production & Operations, Accounting & Finance, Economics, International Business, Information Technology, Social Sector and other areas relevant to the theme.

I take pride to announce the launching of our Management Journal, "**The Siddhant- Journal of Management Principles**" (ISSN- 2249-832X), which will be peer reviewed international bi-annual journal of this college. We are hoping the contributions from authors for the same. Details & instructions for contributors are given on back cover page of this book.

I would like to congratulate all the participants specially authors, and delegates for being part of this conference and hope same in the future.

Finally, I am pleased to acknowledge the encouragement and support received from our colleagues during the conceptual stages of this conference. I wish to thank the organizing committee, participants, students, publisher of this proceeding and never the less CAYMET's management for their motivation.

Best regards

Prof. Atul Kumar

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Research Methodology Strategies in Strategic Management

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ABSTRACT:

This paper review and examine how strategic management researchers apply research methods, and what strategies use as part of the research process, to locate, organize, manage, transform, create, communicate and evaluate research tools, data and information resources. It also analyzes recent developments on research methodology to create scientific knowledge in theory building and practice in strategic management offering an overview of methodologies used in strategic management research. The assessment of strategic management's research methodology is based on a review and analysis of strategies for the incorporation of knowledge of managerial research methods. Finally, the paper identifies and discusses some methodological research issues and reviews future directions on research methodologies in strategic management.

KEY WORDS:

Research Methodology, Research Strategy, Strategic Management.

Innovation as a Strategy in India

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ABSTRACT:

Strategy is best defined as "the software of an organization". It is this software or the common thread that integrates the entire organization. Innovation has to be embedded in this strategy. This article enumerates the drivers of innovation in India and assesses India's current potential for innovation. My views and suggestions are based on empirical studies and extensive research on innovation theory which suggests that rapid innovation is a key strategic driver for organizations and countries alike. This article presents views on 'the factors in India's culture, economy and competitive markets that influence innovation' and suggests what the country can do to enhance innovation capacity.

KEYWORDS:

Blue/Red Ocean Strategy, Competitiveness, Disruptive Innovations, Ingenuity, Patenting Output.

**A Study on the Contemporary Risen Issues in the Mergers and
Acquisitions:
Strategy of the Mexican Business Leaders**

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ABSTRACT:

The corporate strategy is critical to achieving the goals of the firm and must be set out clearly and according to their needs. M & As have become a trend for the growth of Mexican companies, despite having diverse motivations through the description of their implementations in the three largest Mexican firms and the results we achieved demonstrate the effectiveness of this type strategic alliances and other useful items detected less consolidated companies.

KEYWORDS:

Business Strategy, Mergers and Acquisitions, Leading Mexican Companies.

Islamic Banking: Strategic Issues and Challenges in India

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ABSTRACT:

The concept of interest free financing was practiced by Arabs prior to the advent of Islam, and was later adopted by Muslims as a acceptable form of trade financing while the system had been used on a small scale for centuries, its commercial application began in the 1970s. Since then Islamic financing has experienced worldwide acceptance. Islamic banking has the same purpose as conventional banking except that it operates in accordance with the rules of Shariah, known as Fiqh Al-Muamalat (Islamic rules on transactions). The basic principal of Islamic banking is the prohibition of riba (usury or interest). Since Muslims can't receive or pay interest, they are unable to conduct business with conventional banks. To service this niche market, Islamic financial institutions have developed a range of halal (interest-free financing) instruments that conform to Shariah ruling, and therefore are acceptable to their clients. In India though there are no full-fledged Islamic banks. Only 15 to 25 Islamic banks with deposits of about 100 crore are operating all over the India in various states. They are actually non-banking finance companies (NBFCs) which work on interest free banking concepts. But after the rejection of the petition of Subramanian Swami (former union law minister of India) by Kerala High Court, the way to open Islamic banks in India is clear. The Reserve Bank of India (RBI) has recently appointed a committee headed by a chief general manager to look into the prospects of introducing certain Islamic products in Indian banks. This paper focuses on the major strategic issues with Islamic banking system and challenges faced by these banks in India.

KEYWORDS:

Islamic Banking, Interest-Free Financing, Profit-And-Loss Sharing Financing, India.

Strategic management for Today's business: strategies used by luxury brands in India

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ABSTRACT:

Strategic management is a field that deals with the major intended and emergent initiatives taken by general managers on behalf of owners, involving utilization of resources, to enhance the performance of firms in their external environments. It entails specifying the organization's mission, vision and objectives, developing policies and plans, often in terms of projects and programs, which are designed to achieve these objectives, and then allocating resources to implement the policies and plans, projects and programs. The concept of luxury has been present in various forms since the beginning of civilization. Its role was just as important in ancient western and eastern empires as it is in modern societies. With the clear differences between social classes in earlier civilizations, the consumption of luxury was limited to the elite classes. It also meant the definition of luxury was fairly clear. Whatever the poor cannot have and the elite can was identified as luxury. The study is needed to study the importance of strategic marketing in today's business and how it is being used by luxury brands in India. A secondary study will be done about how luxury brands use various strategies to sustain and grow in the Indian market. Journal articles and websites will provide this information. The objective is to study how strategic marketing is so vital in today's business world and also to study the various strategies used by luxury brands in India.

KEY WORDS:

Luxury Brands, Strategic Marketing, International Brands, Disposable Income, Strategy.

Challenges Faced by Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises

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ABSTRACT:

The MSME sector in India, with some exceptions, is characterized by low technology levels, which acts as a handicap in the emerging global market. As a result, the sustainability of a large number of MSMEs will be in jeopardy in the face of competition from imports. Lack of skilled manpower for manufacturing, services, marketing, etc.: Although India has the advantage of a large pool of human resources, the industry continues to face deficit in manpower with skills set required for manufacturing, marketing, servicing, etc. Absence of a suitable mechanism which enables the quick revival of viable sick enterprises and allows unviable entities to close down speedily. Branding and Marketing: Due to very high cost of business acquisition, Low media budget, non participation in International events, the MSME branding and visibility is extremely poor. Information about the market is the core factor of any business activity and it is an essential part of marketing strategy. But according to the survey of Ministry of Small Industries nearly two-third of small businesses considers the lack of market information to be a very severe constraint. SMEs lack the capacity and their owners lack the education to tap sources of relevant information about new products, consumer trends, technological developments etc. Research and Development: Another hurdle faced by the SMEs is low levels of research and development (R&D). R&D is most important requirement of the industrial and service units in the era of globalised market. But the current understanding of R&D activities of SME's is much lesser than the understanding of similar activities of large multinational enterprises. SMEs are still falling down on R&D due to weak links between business and academic research.

KEY WORDS:

Micro, Small & Medium Enterprises, Branding, Marketing, R&D, Skilled Manpower.

Total Quality Management or Business Excellence Strategy Implementation for Enterprise Resource Planning

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ABSTRACT:

Organizations worldwide have been exploring ways to improve business practices to gain competitive edge. One of the most important technological innovations of the last decade has been the emergence of ERP solutions. But implementation of ERP is not just a technological challenge. It's a socio-technological endeavor, which mandates modifying existing applications and redesigning critical business processes to facilitate ERP implementation. Hence, there are organizational and cultural issues, which determine the success of ERP implementation. The main objective of implementing an ERP system is to integrate the organizations business processes and operations for improved business results. But not all organizations have been successful in the ERP implementation. The aim of this paper is to understand the importance of Total Quality Management (TQM) philosophy or Business Excellence Models-Strategy Implementation for ERP Implementation within organizations. There is very little research done where the concept of TQM as a philosophy or Business Excellence strategy implementation, which integrates the concept of ERP implementation. This paper is an attempt to integrate the concept of ERP implementation within a broader perspective of TQM as a part of corporate strategy in an organization. Business Excellence strategy implementation, encompassing the concept of ERP implementation is also discussed. The paper builds upon the foundation on the major research done in the area of TQM or Business Excellence. The concerns & issues for TQM & ERP implementation are discussed. A small case study, of the first company in India to get the coveted Deming Prize based on the integrated Japanese Model for Business Excellence, Sundaram Clayton, is discussed in the paper. The paper attempts to give a holistic perspective of ERP implementation as a part of TQM or Business Excellence Strategy Implementation.

KEYWORDS:

TQM, Business Excellence Models, Strategy Implementation, ERP, Sundaram Clayton.

A Strategic View towards a Digital Library for Higher Education in India

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ABSTRACT:

Digital libraries do not need any physical space to build and can be accessed from anywhere from a single interface. Although there are issues related to Meta-data standards, protocols and copyrights to develop it, but its large volume of texts, images and audio-video resources available at a minimal cost make it a more useful tool to the students, academicians and scholars in Indian scenario too. The need to develop a digital library for up gradation to the information resources available in the academic fields is a far cry to the nation like IBSS Online (International Bibliography for Social sciences Online) published by BLPES with its provision as a national database at BIDs free at the point of use for the whole UK higher education community. The contribution of various study materials available free by the government organizations, library networks, open access journals, databases and books available free from copyrights can make a universal digital library for all the students and scholars in India according to the academic needs and research. The present paper tries to envisage the appropriate strategy to formulate and calling participation of various institutions to make a useful tool for the development of Indian higher education system.

KEY WORDS:

Copyright, Databases, Digital Libraries, Interface, Library Networks, Meta-data, Open Access Journals, Protocols.

Empowering Women Entrepreneurship in Today's World with reference to Aurangabad region - an Empirical Study

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ABSTRACT:

"I measure the progress of society by the progress of women in the society" Dr. B. R. Ambedkar. Gone are the days when the women were confined to the boundaries of four walls and were dependent for their survival in the society. The concept "Chul ani Mul" was followed. Not only this, Sati, Dowry system, Pardah, Devdasis; all sort of restrictions were subjected to women to keep them under the toes of men. In recent times women have absolutely been firm and determined to uproot these evils from the society. It's difficult to believe that the country where the President is a woman, and four major states are governed by ladies, shows that the trend is changing. Today women could be seen right in the field of men dominated world. From the safer jobs of lecturer, banks and hospitals, women are now moving into the industrial area operating big machines and driving trucks, JCB's. Today women own a mom and pop shop in every nook and corner of the city and also a big industrial unit. Small and large women entrepreneurs are now establishing themselves in the domain of marketing, productions, boutiques and what not. The paper tries to focus on an empirical analysis of present, Aurangabad holds for its women citizens. It also projects the future prospects of the empowering women entrepreneurs in Aurangabad.

KEY WORDS:

Women Entrepreneurship, Indian Society, Aurangabad.

Cloud Computing – Way to redefine IT/Computing needs of Business

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ABSTRACT

*Let's say there is a large corporation & employees need the right hardware and software to do their jobs. Buying computers for everyone isn't enough; you also have to purchase software or **software licenses** to give employees the tools they require. Whenever you have a new hire, you have to buy more software or make sure your current software license allows another user. Business has to spend huge money to have this infrastructure in place. Traditional business applications have always been very complicated and expensive. The amount and variety of hardware and software required to run them are daunting. You need a whole team of experts to install, configure, test, run, secure, and update them. But what if, instead of installing a suite of software for each computer, you'd only have to load one application. That application would allow workers to log into a Web-based service which hosts all the programs the user would need for his or her job. Remote machines owned by another company would run everything from e-mail to word processing to complex data analysis programs. It's called **cloud computing**, and it could change the entire computer industry. **How it works & what business can gain from it.** Hardware and software demands on the user's side decrease. The only thing the user's computer needs to be able to run is the cloud computing systems interface software, which can be as simple as a Web browser, and the cloud's network takes care of the rest. Business can get different benefits. New Economics, Pay for what you use. Reduced management- reduced hardware & software means less maintenance & need less manpower. Enhanced Productivity – access any where is using mobiles, laptops & PC's. So bottom-line is increase in the profit. This paper focuses on current applications & potentials of the cloud computing in different IT business sectors.*

KEYWORDS:

Cloud Computing, Software Licenses, System Interface Software.

New Trends in HR with Special Reference to Recruitment and Selection

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ABSTRACT:-

Human resource management is a process of bringing people and organizations together so that the goals of each other are met. The role HR manager is shifting from that of a protector and screener to the role of planner and change agent. Personnel directors are new corporate heroes. The name of game today in business is personnel. With the increase of global job mobility, recruiting competent people is increasingly become difficult, especially in India. Thus, acquiring the right candidate requires proper recruitment & selection strategy which is a major challenge in front of the HR managers. This article focuses on the major 21st century challenges. By creating an enabling culture organizations are also required to work out a retention strategy and employee engagement for existing skilled manpower. HR managers today are focusing attention on policies, motivation, relations, change agent, quality consciousness. Recruitment & selection efforts are reflects in the development of an organization. This is one of the important components in developing Indian Economy, which is growing at rapid pace. This article is concerned with recent trends in recruitment such as outsourcing, poaching/raiding and E-recruitment. Further it discuss about the issues in recruitment & selection and the types of interviews that are used as screening devices for selection recently.

KEYWORDS:

Change agent, employee engagement, retention strategy, E-recruitment, job mobility.

Customer Loyalty Programs – A Strategy for Achieving Customer Satisfaction and Sustaining It

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ABSTRACT:

“The gulf between satisfied customers and completely satisfied customers can swallow a business.” In any business-to-customer (B2C) type of environment, satisfying a customer is the ultimate goal and objective. More often than not, it can be quite an issue. This is perhaps due to the fact that organizations sometimes do not really understand of what actually goes on in a customer's mind. As such, this predicament has provided as a challenging task to most business conglomerates that places strong emphasis on customer relations. Although many researches and studies were conducted on the actual working of the customer's mind, till today it is still a mystery. Therefore, this research paper is focused on how to enhance the customer satisfaction through customer loyalty programs because customer loyalty programs are proving extremely popular among retailers and successful retailers connect with customers via loyalty programs. Loyalty programs are a way for the retailer to encourage the continued patronage of customers. The present study is based on secondary data collected from most authentic sources such as marketing websites, weblogs, e-books, books, newspapers, e-journals, etc. the main Objectives of the study were to explore the substance of loyalty program in the retail industry, to find out various loyalty programs practiced in retail banking sector, to evolve various strategies for different types of loyal customers to serve them efficiently, to study the relationship between business ethics and customer loyalty programs.

KEYWORDS:

Customer Loyalty Programs, Strategy, Customer Satisfaction, B2C, Retail Banking Sector.

Mutual Funds: An Ideal Investment Vehicle

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ABSTRACT:

Since July 1991 economic reforms in India have reached maximum growth in both external and financial sectors. In relation to this evolution of the financial sector the mutual fund industry has occupied an important place. By 2025 in Asia, India is set to emerge as the next super power after to china. Therefore this is a need to re-emphasize on basic infrastructure to protect the economy of the country and also protect the investors' interest. There are a number of investment opportunities all around the investors to achieve the objective of creation of wealth. Among these the mutual fund is the ideal investment vehicle for today's complicated and modern financial scenario. This paper is an attempt to know the concept, reasons for preference of mutual fund investment and related aspects of mutual fund.

KEYWORDS:

Mutual Fund, Investor, Economic Sector, Financial Sector, India.

**A Study focus on Working Capital Management of
Bharat Petroleum Corporation Limited (BPCL)**

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ABSTRACT:

In this study made an attempt to analysis the working capital management of Bharat Petroleum Corporation Limited (BPCL). The period covered in this study is ten years commencing from 1999-2000 to 2008-2009 which is supposed as a normal and stable period. We concluded that the overall position of the working capital is satisfactory, but there is a need for improvement in certain factors. The major portion of the current assets is the form of inventory. The investment in current assets should consider liquidity, profitability and solvency. It is very important to trade off between liquidity and profitability by properly arranging the needed funds at right time period and sources.

KEY WORDS:

Working Capital, Inventory, Investment, Liquidity, Solvency.

Marketing Strategies for the Service Industry to Deal with Recession - An Indian Perspective

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ABSTRACT:

Service Sector in India today accounts for more than half of India's GDP. The fact that the service sector now accounts for more than half the GDP marks a watershed in the evolution of the Indian economy and takes it closer to the fundamentals of a developed economy. Services or the "tertiary sector" of the economy covers a wide gamut of activities like trading, banking & finance, infotainment, real estate, transportation, security, management & technical consultancy among several others. In a recession, consumers become value oriented, distributors are concerned about cash, and employees worry about their jobs. But a downturn is no time to stop spending on marketing. The key is to understand how the needs of your customers and partners change, and adapt your strategies to the new reality. The spillover from the subprime mortgage crisis is weakening both consumer confidence and the consumer spending—much of it on credit—that has been buoying the Indian economy. In this paper researcher has suggested some innovative ideas in these turbulent times & offers a unique opportunity to firms to reinvent themselves in the marketing arena.

This Paper suggests some factors to the Companies when making their marketing plans. Also paper highlights on some suggestions for the marketing strategies a firm can adopt in these difficult times to tide over the crisis. These are just a few ways to dive into the marketing pool of excellence and ride the India story.

KEYWORDS:

Recession, Marketing Strategies, Tertiary sector.

Talent Management for Effective Customer Relationship Management

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ABSTRACT:

CRM is an essential part of modern business management. Customer are the lifeblood of any organization be it a global corporation with thousands of employees and a multibillion turnover, or a sole trader with a handful of regular customers. In order to have effective CRM you need to have required talent in an organization to succeeds in this hypercompetitive and increasingly complex global economy. Now, however along with understanding of the need to hire, develop and retain talented people, there also is awareness that organizations must approach talent as critical resource that must be managed in order to achieve the best possible result. In other words, organizations no longer can afford to assume that always will have the talent they need to execute business strategy. Talent has become a resource that must be managed because it is an increasingly scarce resource. Now talent management seems inevitable given that, on an average, companies now spend over one third of their revenue on employee wages and benefits. Create a new product and it can easily be copied. Lower your price and competitors will follow. But replicating a high quality, highly dedicated workforce is nearly impossible. In essence, the ability to effectively hire, retain, deploy and engage talent at all level – is really the only true competitive advantage an organization can have. This paper will deal with the problems and prospects of talent management and will also highlight untapped potential of talent management in modern business management.

KEYWORDS:

Talent Management, CRM, Customers, Competitive Advantage, Business Strategy.

**Women's Employee Attitudes Headed for Employer- Pay for Child Care
(A Study of Pune City, Maharashtra)**

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ABSTRACT:

The increasing number of women's in the labor market and the rise in dual career couples have prompted many organizations to introduce programmes to help their employees balance their work and personal life. This research focuses on the relationship of women to labour markets and compares employment attitudes for women to the best degree possible, given the latest available of market to help to know the work life balance. Positive employee's views of such initiatives have tended to be assumed rather than demonstrated. These studies assist to observe, how a proposal for a work life balance programs is actually viewed by employees. Drawing on survey data from No. of 300 employees in a shopping centre's in Pune city, the study finds evidence of a range of attitudes. These attitudes are influenced not only by existing and potential control, but also by the possibility of the employees benefiting from childcare as well as their views concerning the role of the organization. Attitudes towards the provision of child care are particularly positive when they inquire about to satisfy difficulties of work organization and are accepted with a flexible approach that takes employees personal boundary in to account.

KEY WORDS:

Womens Employee, Womens Attitude, Day Care for Childern, Work Organization, Work Life Balance.

Impact of Privatisation of Insurance Sector on Indian Economy

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ABSTRACT:

In this paper we have discussed the Impact of privatization in Insurance sector on Indian economy. By critically examining the opportunities available before the privatization of Indian market; we can say that, one of the main reasons for the low insurance penetration in India was the ineffective distribution and marketing strategies adopted by LIC due its monopolistic nature. However, with the entry of new players with the foreign expertise, the insurance market changed almost overnight due the series of aggressive marketing and promotion initiatives which helped to accelerate the increase in insurance penetration. Also tremendous employment opportunities have been created in the field of insurance.

The data used in this paper is Secondary Data. Information has been sourced from newspapers, industry portals, Government agencies, monitoring industry news and developments, and through different websites. The analysis methods used for analysis in the report include historical trend analysis, comparative analysis, judgmental forecasting, and cause and effect analysis. Estimating the potential of the Indian insurance market from the perspective of macro-economic variables such as the ratio of premium to GDP, we reveals that India's life insurance premium, as a percentage of GDP is 1.8% against 5.2% in the US, 6.5% in the UK or 8% in South Korea. From the above, we can conclude that the entry of private players in insurance business is needful and justifiable in order to enhance the efficiency of operations, achieving greater density and insurance coverage in the country and for a greater mobilization of long term savings for long gestation infrastructure prefects.

KEYWORDS:

Insurance, Privatization, Indian Economy, LIC, GDP.

Eco-Tourism in Emerging Tourism Industry: An Analysis Study of Indian Economy

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ABSTRACT:

This research indicates that how new trend as eco-tourism is helping to growing Indian tourism industry. There are also written about the development of heritage as tourist spots, natures based activities, conservative education for tour operators and eco-cultural sustainability. Mass tourism could be based on pleasure, relaxation, religion or carnivals. ET enterprises need to be focused on the natural environment. A resort near seashore or inside a protected forest could meet all the four characteristics of ET while the regular mass visitation to a beach or to a forest temple can only be made eco-friendly.

KEYWORDS:

Eco-Tourism, Global Market, Rural Communities, Tourist Satisfaction, Conservation Education.

A Study of Customer Perspective towards Green Marketing

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ABSTRACT:

Today Green Marketing is a buzz word in ecological business perspective and positive response from the consumer business share is adding an essence to it. Nowadays environmental issues affect almost all the activities of human sphere but very less attention is given towards it. The businesses are now focusing on Eco-friendly measures related to environmental issues faced by the consumers today. It is in the nascent stage right now and researchers would like to contribute some thought provoking contribution in Green Marketing.

The objective of this research paper was to study burgeoning interest among consumer about the Green Marketing. This research empirically examines the factors impacting consumers' purchasing behavior toward green products in Pune region. For this research we interviewed 200 respondents. The respondents are randomly selected. The respondents under study are from Pune City. The study covers both primary & secondary data. A structured form of questionnaire was distributed to 200 employees in Pune City from various areas like Pimpri, Chinchawad, Nigdi, Bhosari, Karve nagar, kothrud, Shivaji nagar, Aundh, Baner. Near about 20 respondents from each area is taken for the study purpose. The target respondents were housewife (36), salaried people (93), businessmen (46) and students (25) from the age category of 20 years to 60 years. All the respondents selected are educated only having graduation and post graduation degree. The secondary data was collected from the published records, journals, magazines & web portals. The data collected was tabulated & analyzed with the help of simple percentage technique. Also Chi square test and Weighted Average test is used for the analysis purpose.

KEYWORDS:

Green Marketing, Environment, Ecology, Eco-Friendly Products.

A Study of Customer Relationship Management (CRM) Practices in State Bank of India in Pune City

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ABSTRACT:

The banking scenario has changed drastically. The changes which have taken place in the last ten years are more than the changes took place in last fifty years because of the liberalization, globalization and automation in the banking industry. Today banking sector is marked by high customer expectations and technological innovations. Technology is playing a crucial role in the day to day functioning of the banks. To face competition it is necessary for banks to absorb the technology and upgrade their services. In today's context banks are following the strategy of customer relationship management which is need of the hour. Customer relationship management is the new paradigm for survival and success, embracing a "share of customer" approach to growth by identifying, protecting and expanding customer relationship.

The current study explores customer relationship management (CRM) practices in SBI Bank in Pune city. Customer relationship management (CRM) is a widely-implemented strategy for managing a company's interactions with customers, clients and sales prospects. It involves using technology to organize, automate, and synchronize business processes—principally sales activities, but also those for marketing, customer service, and technical support. The overall goals are to find, attract, and win new clients, nurture and retain those the company already has, entice former clients back into the fold, and reduce the costs of marketing and client service. Customer relationship management describes a company-wide business strategy including customer-interface departments as well as other departments. The CRM practices survey involves the use of descriptive research design.

KEYWORDS:

CRM, CRM Practices, Retail Banking, Pune.

The Elements of Strategic Planning: - The Study about the Strategists Involved in the Process

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ABSTRACT:

This paper is based on the study about the prominent strategists who are involved in process of strategic planning. Thus Strategic Planning is a challenging and fast developing phenomenon in the corporate world. The dynamic setting of the organization, be it a profit oriented Industrial Corporation or a service enterprise, makes it necessary to manage strategically.

Our discussion of strategic planning begins with understanding of the strategic planning, strategic management and then analyzes the strategic management elements: the strategists who are involved in the process. We also look back into the history and identify some of the highly influencing trendsetters of Indian corporate world who by their long term visibility and strategic thinking not only changed the position of their firms but also set examples for the others.

KEYWORDS:

Strategy, Entrepreneur, SBU, Socio-Political, Technological, Psychological, Leadership, Interpersonal, Time and Decision.

Agritourism: An Emerging Business Industry for Farmers in Maharashtra

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ABSTRACT:

This Research study was designed for Maharashtra farmers interested in developing new or expanding existing Agritourism center as supplementary income source opportunity . This Research paper depicts the basic concept of "agritourism", provides analysis of existing studies and papers, analyzes three case studies of Agritourism centers and makes recommendations for Farmers for further developing Agritourism as an income stream to complement other income-generating activities. The Appendix has a fruitful list of relevant websites and references.

This study describes and analyzes farm projects that offer Agritourism. Some major issues emerge: 1) The centers with different facilities described are located in rural areas near to large urban areas are necessary; 2) Personal satisfaction of tourists through Agripreneurs and employees with their work is important; 3) Conserving the unique character and authenticity of the center is attractive to tourists; 4) Staff with effective people skills is significant; 5) Each Agritourism center seeks participative ways to educate the public about their products and services, 6) Different marketing strategies to make aware and promote Agritourism centers to the urban people are important.

KEY WORDS:

Agritourism , Agripreneurs, U-Picking, Agritouristic Potential , Agritourism Network.

Relationship Marketing: Changing Equations of New Era with Special Reference to Refrigerator

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ABSTRACT:

Relationship Marketing is a buzzword today. This era is characterized by an accelerating change in the radiance of LPG (Liberalization, Privatization, and Globalization). Consumer durables, especially white goods are in enormous demand due to their utility and effectiveness. There is an immense competition generated among the big business tycoons in different nooks and corners of the blue orb. These electronic business houses are putting wholehearted endeavors to excel into the business and trying to gain a competitive advantage through seizing opportunities through customer affinity. Past study by scholars and researchers proves that in each business the customer is a center-point of revenue generation & profit maximization. Mass marketing and even core marketing point of view are being gradually replaced by Relationship marketing.

This research study focuses on role of relationship marketing in white good sector especially concerned with the marketing of Refrigerator. This study also tries to understand the weightages of different parameters connected with strengthening of brand relation with customer. Researcher wishes to understand the underlying decision making ripples going on in customer psyche while purchasing refrigerator. This study is supportive for the companies to understand customer perception through their behavioral patterns.

KEYWORDS:

Relationship Marketing, White Goods, Customer Perceived Value

Study of Risk Factors in Mutual Fund Investment- A Comparative Study of Management's and Investor's Perception

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ABSTRACT:

Investment companies or investment trusts obtain funds from large number of investor's through sale of units. The funds collected from the investors are placed under professional management for the benefit of the investors.

Mutual funds investments are subject to usual risks associated with capital & money market instruments. Risk suggests that a decision maker known the possible consequences of a decision & their relative like hood at the time he makes that decision.

The study attempts to judge the extent of knowledge & perception of various Mutual fund investors regarding risk factors associated with Mutual fund investment.

KEYWORDS:

Mutual Fund, Investment, Risk, Investors, Attitude of Investors.

Entrepreneurship & Innovation: The Base for Differentiation and As a Value Addition Perspective

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ABSTRACT:

India is one of the largest economies in the world and has the third largest GDP in the entire continent of Asia. It is also the second largest among emerging nations. The liberalization of the economy in the 1990s has paved the way for huge number of people to become Entrepreneurs.

Entrepreneurs often bring to mind individuals who are innovative, dynamic, risk-bearing, flexible and creative. Although every entrepreneur identifies an opportunity, utilizes the available resources and converts the opportunity into reality, no two entrepreneurs share the same entrepreneurial style. Whatever the style, all entrepreneurs pursue a dream of converting their vision into reality. With the rise in the need for being innovative, many small firms have also imbibed the virtues of entrepreneurship. Entrepreneurship generates new ideas, employment and also increases productivity. Moreover, with social entrepreneurs seeking practical solutions to social problems, entrepreneurship has evolved beyond just profit-making. For many countries, entrepreneurship has become a key to growth and development. And history reveals that behind every great company, there is a great entrepreneur. However, what makes a great entrepreneur still remains to be answered. While few believe that some aspects of entrepreneurship can be taught, others feel that entrepreneurs are only born. However, the case of NSMW expands its scope to discovering the key to be a successful small scale pharmaceutical entrepreneur & also gives a better understanding on the various aspects that distinguishes successful small scale Pharmaceutical entrepreneur from the not-so-successful ones.

KEY WORDS:

Entrepreneurs, Entrepreneurship styles, Innovative.

Priority Sector Lending

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ABSTRACT:

Banks were assigned a special role in the economic development of the country, besides ensuring the growth of the financial sector. The banking regulator, the Reserve Bank of India, has hence prescribed that a portion of bank lending should be for developmental activities, which it calls the priority sector. The limits are prescribed according to the ownership pattern of banks. While for local banks, both the public and private sectors have to lend 40 % of their net bank credit, or NBC, to the priority sector as defined by RBI, foreign banks have to lend 32% of their NBC to the priority sector. It has been observed that while banks often tend to meet the overall priority sector targets, they sometimes tend to miss the sub-targets. This is particularly true in case of domestic banks failing to meet their sub-targets for agricultural advances. One of the reasons banks often site for not lending to this sector is that recovery is often difficult. The present study is an attempt to study the priority sector advances by the public, private and foreign bank groups. This study is based on the parameters like lending to priority sector by public, private sector and foreign bank groups, targets achieved by public, private sector and foreign bank group NPAs (Non-performing assets), while lending to priority sector. All the parameters have been analyzed for the period, 2009 - 2010.

KEY WORDS:

Priority Sector Advances, Lending, Targets Achieved, Issues, Strategies.

Review of India's Vat Administration - Issues and Concern

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ABSTRACT:

Over 130 countries worldwide have introduced VAT over the past three decades and India is amongst the last few to introduce it. India already has a system of sales tax collection wherein the tax is collected at one point (State Govt.) from the transactions involving the sale of goods. VAT would, however, be collected in stages (installments) from one stage to another. The mechanism of VAT is such that, for goods that are imported and consumed in a particular state, the State Govt. seller pays the State Govt. point tax, and the next seller pays tax only on the value-addition done - leading to a total tax burden exactly equal to the last point tax. As a result of the uncommon nature of VAT system, majority of the States in the country are well aware of its existence, consequently, the low credibility of government makes people contempt the payment and collection of VAT. The purpose of this study is to review the effectiveness of the administration of VAT as it relates to how it can improve government revenue and through more light on its contribution to the economic growth of India. In addition to the preliminary interviews was a review of study relating to the problems of administration and collection machinery of VAT. Simple percentages and chi-square (χ^2) were used for data analysis. There is need to embark on business enumeration in each state with a view to having data base on business. Seminars and workshops so far organized on this issue are narrow its scope and design. There should be functional VAT offices in every council area to coordinate a vigorous campaign to educate people and seek their cooperation. This will no doubt erode the negative attitude that some of the consumers have developed towards VAT. The government should adequately make provision for retrieving the proceeds of VAT from companies and other agents of collection.

Keywords-

Value Added Tax, History, Recent Trends, Administration-economic growth of Small Scale Industries-pros and cons.

Customer Value Management: A Gizmo for Business Excellence

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ABSTRACT:

Company's first task - to Create Customers - Peter Drucker

With the development of economy, original or rational strategic management could not adapt to the complex and ever-changing environment now. The world is changing and becoming more and more unpredictable with each passing day. For a customer centric organization, Customer value from a Marketer point of view is the customer's economic value to the company, demand-oriented view of customer value as the company's or its products' value to the customer. Also, retaining an old customer is as important as acquiring a new customer because a customer's loyalty one lost is very difficult to regain. Loosing a loyal customer is expensive in terms of money as well as mouth to mouth to mouth publicity.

Customer relationship management is helpful for satisfying the customer needs, but it does not include the concept of customer's perceived value. Hence, the new trend of 'Customer Value Management' has emerged. Customer's perceived value is the share of a customer's contribution to an organizations competitive success in the market. The company must define and measure some important factors like its customers retention rate for a period and distinguish the causes of customer attrition so that it can be managed better. An organization must be aware about how much profit it loses when it loses its customer- In Individual customer it is his lifetime value. The aim of customer value management (CVM) is to deliver maximum value to customers, to line up business standards, enhancement programs, business skills, processes, organization and infrastructure in the midst of customer-defined value. In other words, to create the kind of business that can deliver to customer complete satisfaction & delight.

KEYWORDS:

Customer Value, Customer Value Management (CVM), Customer Perceived Value, Customer Retention.

Effect of Downsizing on Employee's Attitude and Morale

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&

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ABSTRACT

Downsizing has become an extremely popular strategy in today's business environment. One of the biggest challenges facing organizations is how to deal with the current business challenges. These challenges range from increased oil prices, political instability and economic recession and their impact on productivity.

Downsizing often generates both a positive and negative Effect. The negative, employees losing jobs and income, creates the loudest general headlines. Along with the obvious workforce negatives, downsizing implies that the company or the overall economy is having serious problems. From a corporate and investor prospective, downsizing can be positive. As expenses are cut, companies may increase their net profits and improve operating efficiency. Investors may also believe that company stock prices may rise in the future as bottom line results improve.

The current study examines whether organizations showing greater consideration for employees' morale and welfare in the downsizing process experience increased labor productivity. Further, because downsizing diminishes human capital and interferes with an organization's social exchange relationships, we posit that attention to employees' morale and welfare will be particularly important for high-performance work systems (HPWS) that rely on human capital for competitive advantage.

A DOWNSIZING such as this one is always difficult for employees.

KEYWORDS:

Downsizing, Employees, Attitude, Morale.

The Siddhant'

(Journal of Management Principles)

AIM AND SCOPE: *'The Siddhant'* - Journal of Management Principles (SJMP) is peer reviewed international journal of "Siddhant College of Engineering" (SCOE), Department of Business Management, Pune, Maharashtra (India). It is being brought out with a view to facilitating effective dissemination of information with regard to various management issues and problem solving methodology relevant for practicing executives as well as for academicians and researchers working in the field of management. This is further to foster better understanding of the principles and practices of management.

The SJMP publishes articles, research papers, abstracts of doctoral dissertations, book reviews, case studies, short communications and bibliography in below mentioned tracks.

Periodicity: *The SJMP* is a biannual journal published in the month of January and July every year.

INSTRUCTIONS TO CONTRIBUTORS

1. The articles, research papers, abstracts of doctoral dissertations, book reviews, case studies, short communications and bibliography should focus on management principles.
2. The SJMP aims at rapid publication of articles while maintaining rigorous peer review process, each article will be subjected to a minimum of two reviews by two individual reviewers.
3. Final decision on acceptance of the paper is with the editorial team. Selected papers will be put in queue for publication, once the article is published author will get a confirmation mail from the corresponding editor.
4. Soft copies of the paper should be in MS Word 2003 or 2007 format and should be sent to the Executive Editor through e-mail. Articles shall be accepted from any country provided submitted in English language only.
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 - f) Brief biographical sketch of the authors
6. Following the front page, from second page, start with abstract of about 200 words exactly conveying the content of article and at least 5 key words.
7. The length of the article should be 5000 – 8000 words, inclusive of tables and figures. Material should be formatted in Times Roman, font size 12 and single spaced.
8. Tables and charts should appear at the end of the text indicating the likely place in the text where it is to appear. All tables and charts should be numbered serially.
9. There will be no footnotes and citations may be made within the text. However, a set of references will have to be given at the end alphabetically and so numbered.
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 - **Articles In Journals:**
Capizzi, M.T. and Ferguson, R. (2005), "Loyalty trends for the twenty-first century", Journal of Consumer Marketing, Vol. 22 No. 2, pp. 72-80.
 - **Books**
Harrow, R. (2005), No Place to Hide, Simon & Schuster, New York, NY.
 - **Chapter in Book:**
Bhattacharya, Asish K, (2004), 'Corporate Financial Reporting' in Reed and Mukherjee, eds, Corporate Governance, 'Economic Reforms and Development' pp 94-115
 - **Published Conference Proceedings:**
Jakkilinki, R., Georgievski, M. and Sharda, N. (2007), "Connecting destinations with an ontology-based e-tourism planner", in Information and communication technologies in tourism 2007 proceedings of the international conference in Ljubljana, Slovenia, 2007, Springer-Verlag, Vienna, pp. 12-32.
 - **Working Papers:**
Moizer, P. (2003), "How published academic research can inform policy decisions: the case of mandatory rotation of audit appointments", working paper, Leeds University Business School, University of Leeds, Leeds, 28 March.
 - **Websites:**
Castle, B. (2005), "Introduction to web services for remote portlets", available at: <http://www-128.ibm.com/developerworks/library/ws-wsrp/> (accessed 12 Nov. 2007).
 - **Newspaper Articles (Authored):**
Smith, A. (2008), "Money for old rope", Daily News, 21 January, pp. 1, 3-4.
 - **Newspaper Articles (Non-Authored):**
Daily News (2008), "Small change", 2 February, p. 7.

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About SCOE:

Siddhant College of Engineering, established by CAYMET in the year 2005 with a vision to provide high quality professional education. The college is approved by All India Council for Technical Education, New Delhi, recognized by State Government of Maharashtra and affiliated to University of Pune. The college is located in a very healthy and pleasant Environment. As per university norms, we offer undergraduate courses in Engineering and PG courses in Management (MBA) & Computer Application (MCA). College is well-equipped with huge and beautiful buildings, students' common rooms, large playground, sport equipments, hostel buildings, reading room, Lab, Libraries, staff quarters, mess / canteen etc. College has a separate Training & Placement cell for our students to enhance their career. There is regular college bus service connecting to entire land mark place in Pune city and Pimpri-Chinchwad Corporation area.

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